

Local Population Studies Society

ISSN: 0143-2974

e-mail: editor@localpopulationstudies.org.uk

Date: March 25th, 2024

LETTER OF ACCEPTANCE

To, Authors,

Mamatov Bakhadir Safaraliyevich
Sayidov Bahodir Qodir o'g'li,
To'rayev Qahramon Fayzullayevich,
Abduazimova Dilorom Hasanboyevna,
Xolboyev Nuriddin Suyunovich

I am pleased to inform you that your manuscript titled: **“Scientific-practical research of the history and stages of development of national music art”** has been accepted for publication in the subsequent issue of International Journal of Managerial Finance (Indexed in Scopus). The period of publication of your scientific work in the next issue of the journal is from 30 to 60 days.

The editors of the journal warn that, taking into account the renewal period of the journals in the Scopus database, the accepted articles may be delayed for a certain period of time. Scientific works of authors are protected on the basis of journal rights. The renewal period of journals in the Scopus database will be announced from April 2024.

After reviewing the scientific works of the authors, if the publication is delayed or not published due to technical reasons, 10% of the payment for the publication of the article will be returned to the authors within a period of 1 month to 8 weeks.

With best regards,

Rowena Burgess

Local Population Studies Society

<http://www.localpopulationstudies.org.uk/>